

Consequences of Child Abuse

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Introduction

The consequences of maltreatment can be devastating. For over 30 years, clinicians have described the effects of child abuse and neglect on the physical, psychological, cognitive, and behavioural development of children. Physical consequences range from minor injuries to severe brain damage and even death. Psychological consequences range from chronic low self-esteem to severe dissociative states. The cognitive effects of abuse range from attentional problems and learning disorders to severe organic brain syndromes. Behaviorally, the consequences of abuse range from poor peer relations all the way to extraordinarily violent behaviours. Thus, the consequences of abuse and neglect affect the victims themselves and the society in which they live.

Many complexities challenge our understanding of factors and relationships that exacerbate or mitigate the consequences of abusive experiences. The majority of children who are abused do not show signs of extreme disturbance. Research has suggested a relationship between child maltreatment and a variety of short- and long-term consequences, but considerable uncertainty and debate remain about the effects of child victimization on children, adolescents, and adults. The relationship between the causes and consequences of child maltreatment is particularly problematic, since some factors (such as low intelligence in the child) may help stimulate abusive behaviour by the parent or caretaker, but low intelligence can also be a consequence of abusive experiences in early childhood.

Psycho Social Consequences

Some studies suggest that certain signs of severe neglect (such as when a child experiences dehydration, diarrhoea, or malnutrition without receiving appropriate care) may lead to developmental delays, attention deficits, poorer social skills, and less emotional stability. Consequences of physical child abuse have included deficiencies in the development of stable attachments to an adult caretaker in infants and very young children (Cicchetti, 1989; Cicchetti and Barnett, 1991; Crittenden and Ainsworth, 1989). Poorly attached children are at risk for diminished self-esteem and thus view themselves more negatively than nonmaltreated children. In several studies, school-age victims of physical abuse showed lower self-esteem on self-

report (Allen and Tarnowski, 1989; Kinard, 1982; Oates et al., 1985) and parent-report measures (Kaufman and Cicchetti, 1989), but other studies found no differences (e.g, Stovall and Craig, 1990).

The consequences of neglectful behavior can be especially severe and powerful in early stages of harm the development of bonding and attachment between a child and parent, affecting the neglected child’s expectations of adult availability, affect, problem-solving, social relationships, and the ability to cope with new or stressful situations (Aber and Allen, 1987; Main et al., 1985). One study by Rohner (1986) has presented impressive cross-cultural evidence of the negative consequences of parental neglect and rejection on children’s self-esteem and emotional stability.

In a prospective study of the qualitative range of caregiving in a high-risk sample, Egeland and Sroufe (1981a) identified a group of mothers who were psychologically unavailable to their infants. These mothers were detached and unresponsive to their children’s bids for care and attention. Children from this group were compared with physically abused, neglected, verbally rejected, and control groups from the same high-risk sample. Using multiple measures across different situations and outcome measures designed to assess the salient developmental issues of each age, the results indicated that children in all maltreatment groups functioned poorly (Erickson et al., 1989). Over time their functioning deteriorated. There were many similarities in terms of the pattern of development between the maltreatment groups, but there were also a number of interesting differences.

Nearly all the children in this study whose mothers were psychologically unavailable were anxiously attached at 18 months of age, with the majority of these classified as anxious avoidant (86 per cent). These children were observed with their mothers in a problem-solving situation at 24 months and a teaching task at 42 months and were found to be angry, noncomplacent, lacking in persistence, and displaying little positive affect. One of the most dramatic findings for these children was the nearly 40 point decline in performance on the Bayley Scales of Infant Development between 9 and 24 months. In the preschool classroom, these children presented varied and serious behaviour problems.

Effects of Witnessing Domestic Violence

Not much is known about the psychosocial status of siblings of abused children. Several studies suggest that the child’s experience of witnessing violence toward siblings or parents may be as harmful as the experience of victimization itself (Rosenbaum and O’Leary, 1981). Some studies have suggested that children who see violence in their homes may view such behaviour as an appropriate means of resolving conflict and also see violence as an integral part of a close relationship (Groves et al., 1993; Jaffe et al., 1988; Straus, 1992). However, research on the effects of a child’s witnessing family violence is contradictory and characterized by methodological flaws. In many studies of the effects of observing family violence, for example, the child subjects are often themselves the victims of physical child abuse.

A few studies in the area of physical aggression and violence suggest that siblings of aggressive children exhibit high rates of aggressive/oppositional behaviour (Patterson et al., 1989; Patterson, 1982). These findings have been confirmed in observational studies showing that aggressive and hostile behavior is exhibited by various members of families of aggressive children.

Related evidence examining the role of interparental conflict suggests witnessing verbal hostility and physical violence between parents is associated with significantly higher levels of child internalizing and externalizing behavior on parent rating scales, and lower levels of child competence based on direct interviews (Fantuzzo et al., 1991) compared with witnessing verbal hostility alone. The impact of observing parental conflict and violence has been demonstrated on

various clinical measures of child functioning (see Fantuzzo and Lindquist, 1986; Jaffe et al., 1990, 1991; Widom, 1989c; Wolfe and Jaffe, 1991). Studies have generally not examined whether the results are due to exposure to parental violence, the effects of confounding variables such as child rejection, limited caretaking skills, and parental involvement, or other forms of family conflict associated with a dysfunctional home environment.

Illicit Drug Use or Abuse

Illicit drug use or abuse in adolescence has sometimes been viewed as a form of psychological escape or as a form of self-medication to control negative sensations (Cavaola and Schiff, 1989; Harrison et al., 1989a,b; Singer et al., 1989). Illicit drug use may also result from a need for self-enhancement and improved self-esteem (Dembo et al., 1987, 1989). Drugs may be used to reduce feelings of isolation and loneliness, by providing the adolescent with a peer group, as he or she becomes part of the drug culture (Singer et al., 1989).

In contrast to the sparse literature on adolescent alcohol problems and childhood victimization, several studies suggest a relationship between childhood victimization and adolescent substance abuse, although the results of this research are sometimes inconsistent (Benward and Densen-Gerber, 1975; Cavaola and Schiff, 1989; Dembo et al., 1987, 1989; Gomes-Schwartz et al., 1985; Harrison et al., 1989; Lindberg and Distad, 1985a; Runtz and

Briere, 1986; Sansonnet-Hayden et al., 1987; Singer et al., 1989). One study by Harrison et al. (1989b) of adolescent males in a chemical dependency treatment program found that male victims of sexual abuse used a wider variety of drugs than nonvictims and used more drugs to self-medicate but did not report an earlier onset of drug use. In contrast, Goldston et al. (1989) found that drug abuse was more common among a control group of girls than sexually abused girls. A study of 444 adolescent girls admitted to chemical dependency treatment programs found that sexually abused girls did not differ in the overall prevalence or frequency of substance use from nonvictims, although the victims were more likely to report regular use of particular drugs and to report an earlier age of onset of drug use (Harrison et al., 1989a). These findings of earlier onset of substance use by female sexual abuse victims support the self-medication hypothesis, rather than motivations associated with peer pressure. Sex differences in the use of illicit drugs may be related to differences in socialization experiences, to age-related patterns of drug use, or to actual gender differences in age of onset of drug behavior (Colten and Marsh, 1984).

Intergenerational Cycles of Abuse

A popular belief in both the scholarly and popular literature is that adults who were abused as children are more likely to abuse their own children. As noted in Chapter 4, Kaufman and Zigler (1987) estimated the rate of intergenerational transmission of abuse to be 30 per cent (with a 5 per cent margin of error). This means that about one-third of the individuals who were abused or neglected as children will abuse their own children and that two-thirds will not. “Being maltreated as a child puts one at risk for becoming abusive but the path between these two points is far from direct or inevitable” (Kaufman and Zigler, 1987:190).

Kalmuss (1984) used data from the National Family Violence Survey to explore the relationship between family aggression and severe marital aggression in the next generation. She found that children who observed hitting between their parents were more likely to be involved in severe marital aggression than children who were hit as teenagers. However, the probability of marital aggression increased dramatically when respondents had experienced both types of family aggression.

Studies addressing sexual maladjustment and/or problems in intimate relationships among adults with a history of sexual abuse show little consistency. Studies that find no differences in marital and sexual adjustment often use college student samples, which may reflect less severe abuse or less severe consequences (Trickett, 1992).

Recent studies have indicated that women with histories of sexual abuse before age 18 (especially incest survivors) are more likely to be poor contraception, to have multiple sexual partners, and to have short-term intimate relationships than women with no abuse histories. They were also at increased risk for unintended and terminated pregnancies and for sexually transmitted diseases (Wyatt et al., in press).

Conclusion

Abused children with more positive supports and fewer conflictual relationships were less likely to be depressed than the other maltreated children in the study. The nondepressed maltreated children were also more likely to report that they felt more cared about by their supports than the depressed children. For example, the co-occurrence of alcoholism, antisocial personality disorder, and substance use has been noted among male jail detainees (Abram, 1990).

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1. <https://www.nap.edu/read/2117/chapter/8>